

JOURNAL OF ENGLISH STUDIES

ISSN : 3122-0479

DOI – <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18038303>

Volume 1 No 2 December (2025): Journal of English Studies

<https://joesfudutsinma.com.ng/joes/index.php/one/article/view/49>

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**RHETORICAL STRATEGIES AND FRAMING OF ECONOMIC HARDSHIP IN
NIGERIA AS REFLECTED IN ONLINE CITIZENS' DISCOURSE ON NAIRALAND
FORUM**

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Abstract

This study investigates the rhetorical strategies and framing of economic hardship in Nigeria as reflected in online citizens' discourse on Nairaland Forum. The study adopted van Dijk's socio-cognitive model (SMC) and Entman's framing theory. It explores how users employ language to construct and contest narratives of national suffering. Furthermore, through the observation method, data were drawn from twenty-eight (28) threads of comments under four news headlines related to Nigeria's economic challenges, covering the period between 2023 and 2025. The qualitative method was used to analyse the selected posts and comments. Findings reveal that 'us' versus 'them' polarisation is discursively sustained through name-calling/abusive labelling, metaphorization, and persuasive appeals such as pathos, ethos, and logos. Findings further revealed that users strategically define the problem as economic mismanagement, diagnose its causes in elite negligence and technocratic detachment, make ethical assessments that attribute leadership failure, and propose solutions centred on reforms and improved public welfare. The study concludes that rhetorical and framing strategies not only express citizens' frustration but also reproduce elements of the ideology of endurance and reform, which frames hardship as both a national trial and a call for transformative government. Finally, the study concludes that rhetorical strategies function as a site for ideological negotiation and ethical assessment, revealing the power of everyday digital communication in shaping public perception of economic realities in Nigeria.

Introduction

Economic hardship has remained one of the most persistent challenges confronting Nigeria in recent times. The combined effects of inflation, unemployment, and declining purchasing power have continued to shape citizens' lived experiences and perceptions of the state. However, beyond the economic realities, hardship also exists as a discursive and ethical phenomenon. How people talk about it often reflects social struggles over blame, responsibility, and hope. In this sense, economic hardship is not only experienced materially but also constructed rhetorically within public discourse.

With the rise of digital communication, online platforms have become crucial spaces for expressing, contesting and reshaping public understanding of national issues. Nairaland Forum, Nigeria's most prominent online discussion platform, provides a vibrant arena where users engage in debates about governance, policy, and everyday survival. These discussions are marked by persuasive and often emotional language that seeks to frame hardship in specific ways; whether as evidence of government failure, divine testing, or a temporary challenge that requires endurance. Such framings are rarely neutral; they unveil underlying rhetorical strategies through which users justify, condemn or normalise the nation's economic conditions.

This study therefore investigates how rhetorical strategies are employed in Nairaland forum posts to frame and construct meanings of economic hardship in Nigeria. It reveals how citizens use language not only to express suffering but also to shape collective interpretations of crisis and recovery. Furthermore, this study explores how a digital platform such as Nairaland forum produces or challenges dominant ideology, particularly what may be termed as the ideology of endurance and reforms, which encourages citizens to view hardship as a necessary phase in the

national economic progress. The study's significance lies in its focus on digital vernacular discussion, a space where everyday Nigerians exercise agency in defining their socio-economic realities outside the boundaries of formal media. Moreover, this study examines the rhetorical construction of hardship on Nairaland to contribute to the development of language and linguistics towards the intersection of ideology and digital culture in shaping public consciousness.

While economic hardship in Nigeria has been extensively examined from economic and political perspectives, less attention has been given to how it is discursively and rhetorically constructed in digital public spaces. Much of the existing studies, such as *Nairaland and the Reconstruction of the Public Sphere in Nigeria* by Temple Uwalaka, *On terrorist attack in Nigeria: Stance and engagement in conversation on Nairaland* by Innocent Chiluwa and Akin Odebunmi, *Blogging, civic engagement, and coverage of politics in Nigeria: A study of nairaland.com* by Okorie Nelson, Grace Loto, and Oladokun Omojola, Femi D and Adegboyega Segun A, leave a gap in understanding how language shapes public opinion and perception. However, the emergence of social media and online forums has redefined the dynamics of public communication, providing new spaces where citizens articulate their experiences and reshape the meaning of hardship through everyday language practices.

Nairaland Forum as a Digital Public Sphere

Nairaland is an online forum created by Seun Osawa in March 2005. It has become one of Nigeria's most prominent digital platforms for civic engagement and public debate. As a participatory online space, it extends the boundaries of Nigeria's traditional media sphere by allowing ordinary citizens to deliberate on politics, the economy, and everyday life (Nairaland

Wikipedia). Chilwa and Odebunmi stress that online media platforms such as Nairaland community serve as a digital public that will enable members to discuss sociopolitical and cultural issues that affect their lives. Oyebade argues that Nairaland functions as a public sphere where citizens can vent their frustrations against socio-political issues in Nigeria and indulge the nastiest of their character traits, which they may not be able to express elsewhere.

Public sphere “may be conceived above all as the sphere of private people who come together as a public” (Jurgen Habermus 27). According to (Chilwa and Odebunmi 97), “public sphere refers to a portion of people's social experience in which they assemble to discuss problems of society and consequently motivate political action. Thus, Nairaland serves as a digital space where Nigerians engage in meaningful discussions about socio-political/cultural events that affect their lives. On the other hand, “social media is a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content” (Andreas Kaplan and Michael Haenlein 60). It also refers to “computer mediated technologies that facilitate the creation and sharing of information, ideas, and other forms of expression through virtual communities and networks” (Kietzmann et al. 241). Within Nigeria, Nairaland embodies this participatory function as an online forum where users discuss political, economic and social issues. It serves as a digital public sphere where citizens express opinions, share experiences, and frame national issues through everyday discourse (Okafor and Daramola).

Research on Nairaland foregrounds its linguistic and ideological dimensions. Adebayo observes that users employ code-switching between English, Nigerian pidgin and indigenous terminologies as a means of negotiating identity and dissent (A Sociolinguistic Study of Nairaland). This cross-linguistic feature facilitates what may be termed the ideology of endurance and reform, whereby suffering is reinterpreted as both a collective trial and a hope for

renewal. Similarly, Akinsanya identifies rhetorical strategies such as intensification, perspectivization, and predication in users' framing of blame, responsibility, and national resilience (Media and Hate Speech on Nairaland forum). Furthermore, Heyd's discourse analysis of online identity-making shows how Nairaland users construct belonging and exclusion through narrative and labelling practices (Doing Race and Ethnicity in a Digital Community). Another relevant study from linguistic and sociocultural perspectives is that of Innocent Chiluwa and Akin Odebunmi's investigation on the users frequent negative evaluations of Boko Haram and the attribution of the activities to Islam and portrayal of northern Nigeria as evil and violent people in the Nairaland forum are potential to worsen religious and ethnic relations in Nigeria (On terrorist attack in Nigeria. Stance and engagement in conversations on Nairaland). Likewise, Romanus Aboh, Funke Josephine Oni, and God's gift Ogban work on how Nairaland netizens' language practices demonstrate dichotomous framing and stereotyping of a negative 'them' and positive 'us' through the deployment of different strategies such as name-calling/abusive labeling, metaphorization of political actors and pronominal selection (Framing and Stereotyping of two frontline presidential candidates in Nigeria's 2019 general election: evidence from Nairaland virtual community).

Other studies include: Examining Blogging, Civic Engagement and Coverage of Political Conflict in Nigeria: A Study of Nairaland.com. Which reveals that the level of civic engagement was affected by the prominence given by the moderators of the Nairaland blog site to the stories that were produced (Okarie Nelson, Grace Loto, Oladokun Omojola). Another relevant study is conflict management in the Nairaland virtual community, where I Lamidi's conflict management strategies are used. Strategic actions taken by posters serve as the basic codes for conflict management in the community.

The previous studies above have either examined stance and engagement in conversation on Nairaland, framing and stereotyping of two frontline presidential candidates in Nigeria's 2011 election, evidence from Nairaland, blogging, civic engagement and coverage of political conflict in Nigeria: A study of Nairaland, conflict management strategies in the Nairaland community, etc. However, this paper goes slightly from a slightly different perspective by investigating rhetorical strategies and the framing of economic hardship in Nigeria: evidence from Nairaland forum posts. It also presents an alternative to critical discourse analysis, which has traditionally been used as the theoretical model in analysing political and media discourses. Moreover, previous studies have used either van Dijk's model, Ruth Wodak's approach, content analysis, or several other approaches to drive their analyses of political or media discourse. This present study combined van Dijk's socio-cognitive model and Entman's framing theory as its theoretical framework.

Furthermore, even though these studies provide linguistic insights into critical discourse studies, media and political discourses, they do not focus on how Nairaland commenters rhetorically frame economic hardship in Nigeria. Therefore, this study gap is addressed by investigating the rhetorical strategies employed by Nigerians who use and comment on the Nairaland forum to frame economic hardship, as well as the ideologies that underpin this framing, particularly in relation to the ideology of endurance and reform.

It enriches our understanding of how social media sites such as Nairaland can be studied as a sociocultural site through which the interconnection between language and youth political activism in Nigeria is made visible.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on van Dijk's socio-cognitive model SCM and Entman's framing theory to provide a complementary foundation for analysing rhetorical strategies and ideological framing. van Dijk's approach connects language use with social cognition (mental model, shared beliefs) and social structures (power, ideology, inequality). Furthermore, the theories are relevant because they deal with how identities are constructed and how ideological differences are enunciated as well as framed in media discourses. CDA is a pillar of media discourse that takes a critical approach to language study. Studies have shown that CDA is a highly dynamic technique for analysing how the media frames issues and people, positively or negatively. Similarly, CDA practitioners apply an interdisciplinary approach to the study of discourses which view language as a social practice.

According to van Dijk ideologies are embedded in discourse through mental representations that influence how individuals interpret and produce texts. van Dijk's model of CDA offers insights into how media discourse can be examined by focusing on its structure, in terms of lexicon, syntax and metaphors, as well as descriptions of actors, rhetorical figures and social identities, among other linguistic strategies and constructions, with a view to revealing the rationale behind such discourse content. The model "integrates diverse linguistic theories and methodologies in developing social and discursive processes" (Omolabi 120). He maintains that "van Dijk's model is hinged on cognition, that discourse can influence social interactions and social structures through the same cognitive model, namely: knowledge, attitudes and ideologies (Omolabi 64). It is postulated that, through the concept of cognition, van Dijk focuses on the relationship between discourse structure and social structure. This implies that, in attempting to understand a micro-level notion of such discourse, one must consider socially shared mental representations and personal models based on personal experiences. Thus, according to the

socio-cognitive model, discourse functions through a cognitive interface and through the mental representation of language users as social members. Therefore, this study applies this model to examine how Nairaland users employ rhetorical choices such as their evaluative tone, ideological positioning, or narrative framing to reflect cognitive schemas about government, suffering, and national endurance. Thus, the SCM is used to portray how ideologies are internalised, reproduced or contested through everyday online discourse.

On the other hand, (Entman 53) posits that framing is a process of selecting certain aspects of reality and making them more salient in a communicative text to promote a specific problem definition, causal interpretation, ethical consideration or treatment recommendation for the items described. Entman argued that frames can be identified in four areas: the communicator, the text, the receiver and the culture. The media can shape and alter audience members' interpretations and preferences through priming. He further stresses that framing "is selecting and highlighting some aspects of a situation to promote a particular interpretation" (Entman 90). In contrast, Chong and Druckman 104) posit that, in trying to frame a particular interpretation, the framing effect occurs. Similarly, they emphasise that "framing effects occur when often small changes in the presentation of an issue or an event produce sometimes large changes of opinion". Therefore, this can be applied to how citizens on Nairaland discussion forum use language to shape or position economic struggles into lived reality by strategically defining the problem as economic mismanagement, diagnosing its causes in elite negligence and technocratic detachment, and making ethical assessments that attribute leadership failure, and propose solutions centred on reforms and improved public welfare. Hence, the theory is relevant for examining how economic hardship is represented in Nairaland discussions. Moreover, by identifying rhetorical strategies as framing devices, the study examined how users attribute

blame, justify reform policies, or express empathy, thereby shaping public interpretation of the economic crisis. Therefore, while Entman's model guides the identification of framing functions and discursive patterns in the texts, van Dijk's model interprets these patterns into ideological and cognitive contexts.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research design to interpret how rhetorical strategies and ideological framing are realised through language in Nairaland forum posts about Nigeria's economic hardship. The data for this study were sourced from Nairaland forum, one of the most prominent online discussion platforms. The forum structure, which organises conversations into threads and comment sections, provides rich and spontaneous interactions suitable for rhetorical and ideological analysis.

Using the observation method, the researchers systematically observe and collect relevant posts and comments that focus on issues of economic hardship, such as inflation, fuel subsidy removal, Naira devaluation and government reform policies. Data were drawn from 2023 to 2025, a period marked by economic reforms and heightened public outcry due to hardship. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select threads that explicitly discuss economic issues and contain rhetorical content, such as emotional appeals or ideological arguments. Approximately, thirty (30) threads of comments under four (4) news headlines related to Nigeria's economic challenges were selected. Finally, they were presented thematically, illustrating how rhetorical and framing patterns reproduce or challenge dominant ideological positions within Nigeria's digital sphere. Furthermore, the observation method involves non-participant observation of

discussions on Nairaland. The researchers do not engage in or influence the discussions but record and archive relevant threads for analysis.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The issues surrounding economic hardship as observed in Nairaland forum align with van Dijk's ideological square of us versus them dichotomy and Entman's Framing theory through the discursive strategies of name-calling/abusive labelling, metaphorisation, and pronominal selection as a polarisation strategy. In doing so, a descriptive approach is employed to analyse the data.

Name-calling/abusive labelling

Name-calling/abusive labelling is a discursive strategy used to negatively characterise social actors, groups or institutions through derogatory expressions, moral judgements, or emotionally charged descriptions. Moreover, it functions as a linguistic tool that describes one actor in a positive way and the other in a negative way, according to the speaker's ideological position as shown below.

Excerpt 1: Nigerian Economy in 2014 vs 2024

COMM a: And 'sane' people are still joining the APC that destroyed the Nigerian economy?

Who does this thing for this country?

COMM b: Other men of God like Eneche shouted.

COMM c: Obasanjo has been on his knees, warning them.

COMM d: Obi's warning and pleadings are there.

COMM e: This is why I love Charles Soludo, as stubborn as he is.

COMM f: The greatest enemy of Nigeria and mankind is the APC.

COMM g: Adebajo warned them before he passed away.

The comments construct a discourse of ideological opposition through irony, sarcasm, and emotional labelling, framing APC supporters as irrational in the nation's decline. References to figures such as Enenche, Obasanjo, and Peter Obi operate as validators, strengthening collective blame and legitimising the in-group's stance. The claim that “the greatest enemy of Nigeria and mankind is APC” extends political critique into a universal condemnation, transforming government failure into an ethical crisis. At the same time, the lament “Who does this thing to us for this country?” expresses shared victimhood, fostering communal solidarity among citizens. Even the qualified admiration for Soludo—“as stubborn as he is”—signals selective approval within an oppositional framework. Overall, these comments show how everyday discourse mobilises blame, constructs identity, and frames economic hardship as the consequence of elite failure rather than structural inevitability. Language thus becomes a site of moral struggle, resistance, and civic self-definition in digital spaces.

Excerpt 2: Oluremi Tinubu Donates 21 Buses to Obafemi Awolowo University

COMM a: What's the source of her money? Dear Nigerian taxpayers, Musa's wife don carry your money do blimblim for OAU.

COMM b: Keep daydreaming! It's amusing that, even at this juncture, few of you still think PBAT (GCFR) won't get re-elected.

COMM c: That aside, what benefit does this have on the Nigerian student? ASUU—even though they can be annoying—are on strike, and this ‘donation’ helps to solve that?

COMM d: Everything about this government is a joke rally.

COMM e: Dammm, this wouldn't give her husband the second term he so desires. You dey play, you think say na Jonathan.

COMM f: Tinubu enjoys the sight of suffering humans and thrives in and through their poverty.

COMM g: Let’s ask Reno, their family documentary video producer.

These excerpts show how name-calling and abusive labelling function as discursive tools of delegitimisation, mockery, and moral judgment within polarised political discourse. The comments collectively construct a narrative that presents the ruling elite, specifically the Tinubu family, as corrupt, performative, and bankrupt. Through a combination of sarcasm, ridicule, and personalised insults, commenters linguistically position themselves as defenders of truth and public morality against perceived state hypocrisy. In the comment “What's the source of her money? Dear Nigerian taxpayers, Musa’s wife don carry your money go do blimblim for OAU,” the substitution of “Oluremi Tinubu” with “Musa's wife” enacts discursive decline, stripping the First Lady of institutional identity. The Pidgin phrase “don carry your money go do blimblim” reframes philanthropy as ostentation, positioning the elite as exploiters of public funds. Similarly, the expression “Everything about this government is a joke rally” reduces governance into a metaphor of mockery, enacting van Dijk's ideological square by contrasting a virtuous public with an incompetent ruling class.

Metaphorisation as a Discursive Strategy

Metaphorisation is a way of describing social actors and their ideological inclinations.. This is exemplified below:

Excerpt 3. Hardship will soon be over, Shettima assures Nigerians.

COMM a: ... With crude price dropping and output declining below OPEC quotas, serving those debts will eat into already thin fiscal buffers. You can't build prosperity on shrinking export income.

COMM b: People who have never experienced hardship in their lives are telling suffering Nigerians to bear with them.

COMM c: Imagine how Tinubu spoke highly of Buhari in 2015, named PDP 'Poverty Development Party'.

COMM d: This mannn! Didn't even mention INTERNAL SECURITY of the deadliest monster staring Nigerians in the face every day.

COMM e: Yes... another level of hardship is yet to come... evil and wicked APC govt. Very incompetent n useless.

COMM f: Na today we started hearing Nigeria go better. Give us a timeline if this is not wishful thinking.

COMM g: Presently, only the Presidency, State Governors and LG chairmen are living large while the populace is living in limbo. Same rubbish they were saying under Buhari Audio promise.

In these excerpts, metaphors such as “serving those debts will eat into already thin fiscal buffers” and “you can’t build prosperity on shrinking export income” animate the economy as a living, deteriorating body—suggesting fragility, depletion, and self-destruction. Similarly, phrases like “living in limbo” and “audio promise” evoke psychological and moral dimensions of suffering, exposing governance as detached, deceptive, and ethically hollow. These metaphorical framings position the public as victims of state mismanagement while casting political elites as exploitative villains within van Dijk’s ideological square.

Excerpt 4: Tinubu's reforms, despite early gains, have not lifted Nigerians out of poverty.

COMM a: Reforms should not only balance the books, they should change lives. Economic transformation must be felt in households, not just seen in headlines.

COMM b: The missing ingredient in Nigeria’s reform agenda is delivery discipline.

COMM c: In essence, macroeconomic gains have not translated into macroeconomic relief. The books may be balanced, but the kitchen tables remain empty.

COMM d: The reality in Nigerian markets and households tells a different story. The statistics show promise, but the streets show pain.

COMM e. ... growth is returning, the Naira is stabilising, and reserves are rising. On the other hand, it revealed a painful truth.

COMM f: This paradox between progress and poverty has become the defining story of Nigeria’s current economic reform journey.

COMM g: ... With basic items such as rice, maize and yams, now far beyond the reach of average families. Transportation and energy costs have doubled, while small businesses struggle with rising input costs and shrinking margins.

These excerpts reveal how metaphorical framings construct the experiential dimensions of Nigeria's economic discourse. The contrastive metaphors “balance the books” versus “change lives” show the tension between bureaucratic efficiency and human welfare, redefining reform as failure when detached from social impact. Similarly, the “missing ingredient” symbolises inefficiency and a lack of coordination. The expression “The books may be balanced, but the kitchen tables remain empty” shows ideological critique. It compares institutional success against household deprivation, using the imagery of “books” and “tables” to bridge macroeconomic abstraction and lived reality. The same contrast is extended in “statistics show promise, but the streets show pain,” where alliteration strengthens the opposition between official narrative and experiential truth. Images of scarcity—“beyond the reach of families” and “shrinking margins”—translate economic decline into embodied experiences of distance and suffocation.

Persuasive Appeals as a Rhetorical Strategy

Persuasive appeals in media discourse are central to how social actors organise sentiment, construct validity, and justify competing interpretations of hardship. In line with van Dijk's socio-cognitive approach and Entman's framing theory, persuasion operates ideologically through three interconnected appeals: pathos (emotional appeal), ethos (credibility appeal), and logos (logical appeal). Each appeal serves as a strategy for constructing a stance and influencing

public perceptions of who bears responsibility, who suffers, and what solutions appear desirable or credible.

Pathos: Emotional Appeal as a Strategy of Identification and Mobilisation

COMM a: "... With crude price dropping and output declining below OPEC quotas, serving those debts will eat into already thin fiscal buffers."

COMM b: "People who have never experienced hardship in their lives are telling suffering Nigerians to bear with them."

COMM c: "Imagine how Tinubu spoke highly of Buhari in 2015, named PDP 'Poverty Development Party.'"

COMM d: "Didn't even mention internal security, the deadliest monster staring Nigerians in the face every day."

COMM e: "Yes... another level of hardship is yet to come... evil APC govt. Very incompetent and useless."

In these comments,, pathos reveals itself through an emotionally charged lexicon that presents suffering and outrage. They employ negative terms such as "wicked," "evil," "useless," "in limbo" to construct a plain dichotomy between the governing elite and the suffering populace. Similarly, the emotional intensity identifies hardship, while transforming economic struggle into an existential crisis tied to leadership betrayal. This polarisation strengthens the "us versus them" schema we (the suffering citizens) are right and enduring, while they (the elite) are corrupt and separated. On the one hand, Entman's framing functions are evident in the discourse, which defines the problem (elite greed and mismanagement), assigns responsibility (to the

government), and evokes judgment (wickedness and failure). Therefore, through pathos, participants reframe economic decline not as an impersonal structural event but as an ethical violation.

Ethos: Invoking Credibility and Authority

COMM a: “Obasanjo has been on his knees warning them,”

COMM b: “Peter Obi’s warnings are there.”

COMM c: “Soludo, as stubborn as he is...”

COMM d: “Okonjo said they were borrowing to pay salaries”

COMM e: “Sanusi said it must never be more than 3%,” “The World Bank says 5% is acceptable.”

In these excerpts, ethos operates through appeals to expertise, historical memory, and ideological credibility. References to respected figures such as Obasanjo, Soludo, Peter Obi, and Sanusi construct an ethical and technocratic authority that legitimises critique. These personalities, framed as visionary witnesses rather than biased actors, give credibility to public disillusionment. Likewise, the invocation of global institutions such as the IMF, the World Bank, and Okonjo-Iweala situates the discussion within an international ethos of expertise and accountability, portraying the speakers as informed and rational commentators.

Logos: Rationalisation and Logical Framing of Economic Reality

Logos operates through analytical and contrastive reasoning, revealing contradictions between macroeconomic indicators and lived experience. Let us consider the following comment from the data.

COMM a: “Reforms should not only balance the books; they should change lives.”

COMM b: “The missing ingredient in Nigeria's reform agenda is delivery discipline.”

COMM c: “Macroeconomic gains have not translated into relief; the books may be balanced, but the kitchen tables remain empty.”

COMM d: “Statistics show promise, but the street shows pain.”

In these excerpts, logos emerge through logical contrasts such as “balanced books vs empty tables” and “statistics vs streets,” which show the disconnection between technocratic success and lived hardship. These rational oppositions invite cause-and-effect reasoning, positioning citizens as critical evaluators of policy credibility. Argumentation shifts from emotional critique to analytical judgment, foregrounding observable social outcomes over abstract fiscal rhetoric.

Discussion and Conclusion

The findings reveal that Nairaland’s discourse on economic hardship functions as an ideological negotiation of power, accountability, and identity. Through emotionally charged language, metaphor, and persuasive appeal, users transform online discussion into a collective act of political critique. Drawing on van Dijk’s socio-cognitive theory, the analysis shows how participants construct the “self” as a morally conscious and suffering citizen and the “other” as a corrupt and insensitive elite. This us-versus-them polarisation is sustained through sarcasm, labelling, and negative other-presentation, which legitimise anger and strengthen collective

identity (van Dijk 18). In line with Entman’s framing theory, the study finds that users define the problem (economic mismanagement), diagnose causes (elite negligence and technocratic detachment), make ethical assessments (leadership failure), and suggest remedies (welfare-improving reforms). Metaphors such as “balanced books vs empty tables” and “living in limbo” reconstruct abstract economic concepts into lived experiences of deprivation, reframing hardship as an ethical and human crisis rather than a statistical challenge (Entman 52). Persuasive appeals further sustain this ideological construction. Pathos evokes empathy and collective frustration through emotive metaphors; ethos draws credibility from respected figures such as Obasanjo and Soludo; and logos exposes contradictions between official claims and observable realities. Collectively, these appeals reflect what van Dijk terms the ideological management of knowledge—a cognitive process that legitimises dissenting worldviews while contesting dominant narratives (van Dijk 31). Nairaland’s anonymity and interactivity increase these dynamics by removing social hierarchies, allowing citizens to express discontent without fear of retribution. This discursive freedom fosters creativity, satire, and resistance, making digital spaces like Nairaland vital arenas for democratic expression.

In conclusion, the discourse on economic hardship on Nairaland goes beyond casual commentary. It operates as a performative act of ideological resistance, where citizens reclaim interpretive authority, critique government failures, and construct counter-narratives grounded in empathy, credibility, and reason. Through framing and rhetorical strategies, ordinary users turn online dialogue into civic participation and moral accountability.

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